

Special Article

Inception of First Human Milk Bank in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Breast milk has been vital to life since the beginning of humanity and is the best food for all types of newborns like mature, premature, Appropriate Gestational Age, Large for Gestational Age and Small for Gestational Age. Sometimes it is very difficult to have breast milk for newborns due to critical illness or loss of mother and donated breast milk may be lifesaving of these precious newborns.

Human milk bank (HMB) is a service which collects, screens, processes, and dispenses donated human milk. There are more than 500 human milk banks in the world, but limited number is present in Muslim countries like Iran, Iraq, Pakistan, Kuwait, and Malaysia in small scale. Because western and European pattern human milk bank is not possible in Muslim countries like Bangladesh as Islamic law does not allow consumption of unidentified donated milk from multiple donors, so religiously compliant and conditionally identified milk bank (CIMB) is the alternative option to save the lives of critically ill newborns when their lives are not sustainable without breast milk. In this type of milk bank every mother's milk is processed and stored separately and one mother's milk is to provide to one baby with counseling of both families regarding the Islamic law of prohibition of future marriage between milk siblings. For future reference documents related to this issue is given to both families and utmost dedication is maintained to preserve data in all steps.

It is very much challenging and tough to cross hurdles to establish human milk bank in a Muslim country like Bangladesh, but we must go forward. As religiously compliant and conditionally identified human milk bank is legal in Islamic law, this kind of milk bank is essential to establish to save the lives of critically ill newborns where there is no alternative of breast milk to save their lives.

Key words: Human Milk Bank, Conditionally Identified Milk Bank (CIMB), Milk siblings.

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Introduction:

Human milk banks play an essential role by providing human milk to infants who would otherwise not be able to receive human milk. The largest groups of recipients are premature infants who derive very substantial benefits from it. Human milk bank or breast milk bank is a service which collect, screens, store, processes, and dispenses human milk donated by nursing mothers who are biologically related or not related to the recipient infants.¹ The World Health Organization (WHO) states that the first alternative to a biological mother not being able to breast feed is the use of human milk from other sources.² Recently published research and systematic reviews have reinforced the conclusion that breastfeeding and human milk are the reference normative standards for infant feeding and nutrition.³ The strict quality control procedure in milk banks ensure the safety of donor milk.⁴

Beneficial effects of donor milk remain significant and donor milk is still highly preferable when own mother's milk is not available.⁵

Human milk is the best food for all types of newborns lives like, preterm or term babies, small for gestation (SGA) or large for gestational age(LGA) babies.⁴ The World Health Organization estimates that if every woman optimally breastfed her baby the lives of 800,000 young children could be saved every year.⁶⁻⁸ Mother's own milk should be the first choice for all neonates including preterm newborn children, when a mother's own milk is inaccessible or hard to find for different reasons, the following best choice is donated human milk (DHM) as a protected option following World Health Organization (WHO).⁹ When a mother gives birth prematurely, she may have difficulty providing breast milk for her child. Pasteurized donor human milk (DM) is a better feeding alternative. Human milk banks in North America pool the milk from up to 5 women before distribution, a concept which does not pose a problem for most living in the Western world.¹⁰

Breast milk is fundamental to the improvement of the infant's immature immune and digestive system⁸ and provides an abundance of bioactive

factors, which support and enhance the deficient immunologic system of the newborn thus decreases child mortality.¹¹ Human milk has a protective effect for premature infants who are at risk of necrotizing enterocolitis and sepsis, two medical conditions associated with high rates of mortality.³ The American Academy of Pediatrics has also recommended donor human milk (DHM) in part, due to a reduction in occurrence of NEC.¹² It is expected that better to give mother's own milk if impractical at that point give DHM or milk sharing.¹³ Meta analysis of data from eight trials shows that feeding with others milk rather than donor breast milk increases the risk of necrotizing enterocolitis in preterm and LBW infants.⁸ There are many circumstances where milk from the infant's own mother is not available or sufficient. Milk donated by other women will then fill the gap.¹⁴

At present there are more than 500 Human milk banks over 38 countries worldwide and 1st Human milk bank was established in 1909 in Vienna, Austria. Brazil has an extensive network of 217 milk banks and is considered to have the most cost-efficient system of milk banking in the world.¹⁵ But there are limited human milk banks in the Islamic countries like Kuwait, Pakistan, Iran and Iraq. Turkey and Malaysia are planning to establish human milk bank.

The Islamic tradition recognizes breast milk as the optimal source of nutrition for infants, yet religious reservations have prevented the establishment of human milk"based industry in Muslim countries. Religiously compliant and conditionally identified human milk bank is different from Human Milk Bank of Western countries where milk from many moms are mixed with one another and pasteurized together.

Strategies are taken to establish a human milk-based industry in the Muslim world for the best interests of infants and children while respecting the tradition of milk kinship.^{16,17} One possible option is milk from just one donor would be given to a baby, and the identity of the donor and recipient must be made available.¹⁸

Rearing a baby and a full-time job can be challenging anywhere in the world, but in Bangladesh, the rights afforded to working mothers lag way behind.⁷ There are around 3.6 million ladies employed in the readymade garments industry alone, making it the single biggest employer of women in the nation.¹⁹ These mothers need to work extended periods of time, and numerous industrial facilities do not have crèche facilities for young children to empower mothers to convey their kids to work. In this circumstance, they can donate their surplus milk for child of other people who can utilize it. Milk banks are the most institutionalized and safest method of milk sharing and milk banks function as repositories of donated milk.¹⁴

Rationale of establishing HMB in ICMH:

NICU of ICMH provides services to inborn and out born babies. Being a level III care center, it treats all critically ill newborns that require utmost care in term of nutrition with Breast Milk. But in case of mother's death, we face difficulties to provide breast milk to those innocent critically ill newborns where there is no alternative of breast milk to save their lives. Another scenario is mother has enough milk, but her baby is unable to breastfeed or having feeding intolerance, at that moment she has to discard her precious milk to get relieve from engorged breast or breast abscess. If there is a human milk bank by fulfilling the Islamic law collected and preserved breast milk

can be used for their own and other critically ill babies when indeed.

Requirements for establishment of an ideal human milk bank:

Infrastructure:

- Well illuminated rooms with at least 500 square feet carpet area, situated near or within NICU/KMC corner having air-conditioning facility. It should be compartmentalized into:
 - A waiting area with reception and crèche,
 - Counseling area,
 - Area for donation/ collection (with maintenance of privacy for donor),
 - Area for equipment.
- A toilet block would be preferable within the facility.

Logistics:

- Pasteurizer with special shell to pasteurize small amount Individual mother's milk
- Laminar air flow machine
- Hot air oven
- Special steeliness steel container with heat and water resistant Id number
- Deep freezer
- High quality breast pump
- Data entry system and ID card printer.

Pasteurizer with special shell to pasteurize small volume of milk like 25 ml.

Laminar air flow to combat external contamination

Hot air oven to sterilize milk containers at 300° c Temp

Special stainless-steel container
With heat and water resistant
ID sticker

Deep freezer to store milk at -
26° c Temp for 18 months.

High quality breast pump to
express minimum 250 ml milk
within 15 minutes

Manpower: Trained physicians, nurses, one computer operator and one counselor to run this bank properly.

Process to establish HMB in Bangladesh:

The idea of establishing an exceptional human milk bank in Bangladesh was conceived in January 2019 following visit to two HMB, Mumbai of India and Valencia of Spain. After detail literature and Islamic law review, application was submitted to Director General of health Services (DGHS) and Ministry of Health and Family Welfare for the approval of HMB. An application was also submitted to Islamic foundation for religious clarification and to get Halal certificate. Several unofficial meetings were held with them and Islamic group. Instruments were collected and installed in 1st week of November 2019, training of manpower on HMB was completed on 3rd week of same month. After crossing all hurdles HMB was started on 1st December 2019.

Capacity of HMB at ICMH:

Daily near about 50-60 containers (50-250ml) milk may be collected and preserved which will be sufficient for 50-100 newborns.

Rules and Regulations:

The human milk bank is running according to Islamic law and in the light of humanity. Critically ill newborns admitted in NICU of ICMH are included in this bank whose lives are not sustainable without breast milk. This Bank is not generalized for all babies. Verse 23 of Surah An-

Nisa is being provided to both Donor and Recipient Group to follow the Islamic guideline and to avoid future marriage within milk siblings. The following rules are being followed-

- Activities of this bank has been conducted under the supervision of Ministry of Health and welfare, Director General of Health Services and Islamic Foundation. Only the milk of mother with female infant is provided to female babes and vice versa. In case of other religions their law is to be followed.
- No financial exchange is done between donor and recipient group.
- Milk of one mother is given to one baby only.
- Donor and recipient receive ID card with specific and unique ID mentioning address of both groups along with telephone numbers and email ID.
- Milk is collected from mother after proper medical checkup, screening, and consent. Individual mother's milk is collected, processed by pasteurization, and preserved separately in separate food grade container with sticker. Consent paper including photograph of donor and recipient is given to both groups. Every year annual report will be provided to district marriage registration authority.
- All information is to be preserved in ICMH NICU website- www.nicuicmh.org and in milk bank apps for future reference.

- CD is given to both groups with their recognition. (Video)
- Milk mother's and father's name are mentioned in the hospital discharge paper along with own father's and mother's name.
- In near future measures will be taken to include milk mother's and father's name in national ID card according to need.
- The milk bank is under the supervision of a committee consisting of one Mufti, Journalist, Nutritionist, Pathologist, Public representative, Coordinator of this bank, Head of the department of Paediatrics, Joint Director, Director and Executive director of ICMH.

Measures to prevent future marriage between milk siblings

First both donor and recipient group will be informed that it is illegal to marry milk sibling one another and according to Islamic law it is a great sin. After counseling if both groups agreed and know the consequence of taking donor milk in the view Islamic law and confirm us to take steps to prevent future marriage between milk siblings and other women associated with breastfeeding related relationship those who are illegal according to the Islamic law, only then a complete information pack containing consent form, donor and recipient ID card, donor & recipient voter ID card, hospital discharge paper mentioning milk mother's name along with baby's own mother's and father's name, donor and recipient photos, web address -<http://www.nicuicmh.org>, milk bank apps- **BHMB** will be provided to donor and recipient for their future reference. To maintain Islamic law strictly, printed

copy of Surah An-Nisa that is the Surah-4, verse-23 of Al-Quran with Bengali meaning and English version of Arabic will be given to both parties to follow the order of the Holy Quran.

Surah An-Nisa, verse-23: Forbidden to you (for marriage) are: your mothers, your daughters, your sisters, your father's sisters, your mother's sisters, your brother's daughters, your sister's daughters, your foster mother who gave you suck, your foster milk suckling sisters, your wives' mothers, your step daughters under your guardianship, born of your wives to whom you have gone in - but there is no sin on you if you have not gone in them (to marry their daughters), - the wives of your sons who (spring) from your own loins, and two sisters in wedlock at the same time, except for what has already passed; verily, Allah is Oft-Forgiving, Most Merciful.

Collection of breast milk:

After proper counseling, checking suitability for donation, getting written informed consent, history taking, physical examination and sampling for laboratory tests, the donor is sent to designated breast milk collection area in the milk bank or in the milk collection center. Breast milk is collected by trained staff with hygienic precautions, by hand expression. Manual expression is a low cost and effective method of expression and associated with less risk of contamination. Good quality breast pumps can aid larger collection of breast milk from donors who want to regularly donate. With pumps simultaneous bilateral breast expression is more efficacious than sequential breast expression. Milk is collected in properly labeled sterile container and transported to HMB under cold storage condition. All data of donor and recipient with contact number is to be maintained in soft copy and hardcopy.

Recipients of the HMB:

Critically ill neonates admitted NICU of ICMH

Abandoned neonates

Babies whose mothers died in the immediate postpartum period

Milk Processing:

All batches of collected raw breast milk is refrigerated immediately till the serological report comes negative. Fresh raw milk will not be added to the frozen milk since this can result in deep freezing with hydrolysis of triglycerides. For sick or preterm babies, it is advisable to use a new container for each pumping.

Individual mother's milk is pasteurized in individual container and no pooling and mixing is carried out from multiple donors. Pasteurization is carried out by Holder's method. Microbiological screening of donor milk is done before (if there is no cost constraint), and as soon as possible after pasteurization. No growth is acceptable in post-pasteurization microbiology cultures.

Storage:

Pasteurized milk awaiting culture report is kept in dedicated freezer/freezer area taking precaution not to disburse it till the culture is negative. Storage should be done in the same container that is used for pasteurization. It is advisable not to transfer processed milk in other containers as it has risk of contamination. Culture negative processed milk should be kept at -26°C in tightly sealed container with clearly mention of expiry date and other relevant data on the label. It can be preserved for 3 to 18 months. Random cultures of preserved milk before disbursement can aid quality assurance.

Disbursal:

Processed milk should be disbursed at physician's requisition from NICU physician after informed consent from the parents of the recipient. Preterm baby should preferably get milk from preterm donors. It should be done on First-in-first-out basis from the storage. Transport of milk should be done under cold storage in the same pasteurized container till its use. Frozen milk should be thawed by either defrosting the milk rapidly in a water bath at a temperature not exceeding 37 centigrade, or under running lukewarm water taking care that the cap of the container does not come in contact with the water as it is likely to get contaminated.

It should never be thawed in a microwave as this result in reduction in the IgA content of the milk. Milk should not be refrozen after being thawed as this increases the hydrolysis of the triglycerides in the milk. While bringing to room temperature,

it should be gently agitated to make a homogenous mixture before use.

Labeling and record keeping:

HMB should have an operational objective of ensuring full traceability from individual donation to recipient and maintaining a record of all storage and processing conditions. Written standard operating procedures should be followed. Confidentiality of records should be maintained by the milk bank. Proper labeling at all levels is mandatory. Labels should be water resistant and names and identifying details of donors, dates of pasteurization, batch numbers and expiry date should be clearly readable.

General guidelines for staff of the human milk bank:

Standard operating procedures (SOP) of the bank (which should be displayed at proper places) should be adhered to.

- Hygienic practices like proper hand wash, donning gowns, mask, gloves, trimming nails, locking long hairs should be maintained
- Gloves should be worn and changed between handling raw and heat-treated milk.
- Staff should undergo regular health checks and be immunized against Hepatitis B.
- There should be a program for ongoing training of the staff.

Economic Implications:

Cost effectiveness of using banked human milk in neonatal intensive care units has been documented in western countries, largely due to reduction in the rate of NEC. In a country like ours, the cost of running a milk bank with potential cost-saving due to reduction in NEC, sepsis and duration of hospital stay have not been evaluated. As prematurity and sepsis are two major causes of neonatal mortality in Bangladesh, ensuring exclusive breastfeeding with early initiation will help to reduce the burden of sepsis and neonatal mortality.

Conclusion:

As religiously compliant and conditionally identified human milk bank is legal in Islamic law, so this type of milk bank will save the lives of critically ill newborns where there is no alternative of breast milk is a time bound need.

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